

**A STUDY ON IMPLEMENTATION OF LEAN SIX SIGMA
STRATEGY IN SERVICE SECTOR ORGANIZATION
(DENTAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL)**

SYNOPSIS

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SYNOPSIS/ PREPHASE

INTRODUCTION

The contributions of the service sectors to the world's overall economic growth, and India in particular, have increased significantly over time. It has been recorded that the services sector has accounted for nearly 60 percent increase in GDP in the last two decades. India is also renowned for its IT, Education, Healthcare and Communication services. But to retain a sustainable competitive advantage (Chakrabarty and Tan, 2007) it must enhance the quality of the services provided and the skills of the workforce.

Although the service industry's contribution to the Indian economy is tremendous however it doesn't function smoothly. Inflation, increasing fuel prices, depreciation of the Indian currency, and a fiscal deficit are the major challenges for the private sector, which in turn raises service sector costs (Soni, 2013). Rising sophistication of systems and processes with increasing high-performance demands puts unparalleled pressures and opportunities on organizations sustainable growth. Service organizations will revisit its vision and mission periodically to tackle the highly competitive market.

Studies revealed a great need for the incorporation of quality enhancement tools and techniques in Indian service industries (Talib, Rahman and Qureshi, 2013; Talib, Rahman and Qureshi, 2011). Research in the field of quality resources for the Indian service sector also shows that while the Indian service industries are well aware of the quality assurance initiatives, further efforts need to be made on the implementation of quality management mechanisms and on the continuous improvement of quality practices. As the quench to achieve excellence and thus the competitive advantage the service sector organizations are in toe tip to implement scientific management tools.

AIM

The aim is to develop a research framework for LSS implementation in a dental college and widen the outreach to Service sector. LSS is applied to three departments of a Dental college to make it more productive in terms of quality, sustainability and operational efficiency. Another objective is to reduce the variability and thus make the system more efficient in terms of human capital and economic factors. Executing each task at department level is considered as a pathway towards excellence.

LITERATURE SURVEY

An exhaustive literature review was conducted, with the goal of understanding project definition of LSS and its effect on society. Furthermore, the aim is to bring focus to the research problem, to improve methodology, to broaden knowledge and to reinterpret results. Particular attention has been given to updating LSS literature in the Indian context and the department 's global quality management initiatives. In addition, a more comprehensive analysis of the deliverable LSS (KPIs, CSFs, STTs, and CTQ). A thorough interpretation and identification of these with the LSS framework has been carried out.

METHODOLOGY

Basically, the combination of “Grounded theory method” and “Action research method” are used in this study. These two research methodologies fit in together and have potential to develop effective framework (Butterfield, 2009)

GROUNDING THEORY METHODOLOGY

The researcher starts with some initial constructs in ground theory methodology, studies deeply into organizational actions and events, and progressively tests and develops theoretical constructs. This approach makes use of the experience of both practitioners and multiple data sources. Thus, the current research involves building theory through 'Grounded Theory,' which capitalizes on the rich practitioner-based knowledge of the LSS strategy. 'Grounded theory method' may often include quantitative and qualitative data. These two forms of data are not intended to test each other but to act as supplements through mutual checks. Most importantly, different forms of data on the same topic when compared aid in the theory development

QUESTIONNAIRE BASED SURVEY

Questionnaire based survey is most commonly used in Operation management research (Flynn et al, 1990). This is because it can be sent to many institutions at different locations, standardization of the questionnaire allows for a comparative analysis of responses, flexible time in which respondents can choose their own time, a relatively fast way of gathering data and, in the specific instance of open-ended questions, respondents can answer based on the expertise. The survey served as a beacon for the subsequent case studies.

The survey was conducted by seeking answers from 16 private dental educational institutions and 3 public dental institutions in the southern part of Karnataka, India. The reason for selecting only 3 public dental colleges is, there are only 3 public dental colleges in state of Karnataka. Private colleges outnumber public with a wide margin. The questionnaire was designed with open-ended follow-up conversation, based on Likert scale. The target group was Internal Quality Cell staff who are well versed in statistical techniques and quality measures. Every college had necessitated three responses. One of the simplest methods for determining instrument reliability is the alpha of the Cronbach. Values equal to or above 0.60 is the lower limit usually accepted for exploratory work (Hair et al., 2010). The study's statistical analysis showed that Cronbach's alpha for the instruments products was above 0.7.

ACTION RESEARCH METHODOLOGY (CASE STUDY APPROACH)

Design and method of case study research is an empirical independent investigation that investigates a depth and within its real-life context, particularly when the boundaries are not clear (Yin, 2003). This is the most suitable approach when the study is exploratory in nature and for establishing a conceptual framework

The following three departments been selected for the research after the business case and receiving subservient approval from the university ethical council.

1. Conservative dentistry
2. Endodontics
3. Periodontics

The methodology for the case studies was as follows: constructing the research problem, gearing up the research design, gathering information, analyzing the data, testing and interpreting hypotheses, and enforcing the results. An initial study had been undertaken to establish a business case, which in turn helped define the research concerns. The data from the business case was helpful in determining the busiest departments in dental college.

The data was obtained from the process in compliance with the extensive data gathering plan to clarify baseline results and verify triggers. Detailed analysis of this data has been carried out using

Normality Test, Xbar-R Chart, Value Stream Mapping (VSM), Capability Analysis, Box Plot and Multivariate Chart were used to draw reasonable conclusions (Montgomery and G.C. Runger, 2007). Tools such as Analysis of Variance, GEMBA, TRIZ, two sample Test and Simulation were used and inferences have been made. Minitab statistical software was used in case study analyzes of the data obtained at different levels.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT

A framework is a collection of basic principles of intellectual origin or fundamental assumptions from which acts and discussions can proceed (Popper, 1994). The framework should make organizations more aware of the technique and encourage more managed, timely and demanding implementation of its elements (Aalbrecht, Hejka and McNeley, 1991). The structures and models are frequently used interchangeably. Researchers consider frameworks as useful ways of thinking about processes for modeling purposes, and models as representations of structures attempting to explain or predict component behavior (Rouse and Putterill, 2003).

To develop the conceptual model, the insights gained from literature review, case studies, and surveys were used. Thus, the system developed was validated by 'SEM' (Ruben, Vinodh and Asokan, 2020)

LSS FRAMEWORK and SEM (Structural Equation Modelling)

For this analysis the stated hypotheses are:

H1. KPIs lead to Sustainability

H2. CTQs lead to Sustainability

H3. CSFs leads to Sustainability

H4. STTs leads to Sustainability

The hypotheses mentioned are based on the conclusions drawn from the multiple case studies conducted in a dental college over a timeframe of 2 years. The hypotheses are often presented according to the association and influences that measure the moderating effect between the chosen

constructs. Figure below shows the structural model established and the hypotheses developed using the software module Smart PLS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The hypothesis claimed are verified after performing the validity and reliability tests to ensure that the structural model established matches the survey data collected. This is achieved by measuring the value "t". Based on the t-values obtained, it is apparent that the hypothesized model reflects the data from the survey. According to the conventional statistical table, for endorsing a hypothesis the observed "t" value must be greater than 2. And the "p" value should be less than 0.05. The

proposed hypotheses(H3) for the structural model established complied with this criterion. The results prove that H3 is true at 95% confidence level.

H1- KPIs lead to Sustainability (p = 0.465; t = 0.731)

H2- CTQs lead to Sustainability (p = 0.140; t = 1.480)

H3- CSFs leads to Sustainability (p = 0.034; t = 2.129)

H4- STTs leads to Sustainability (p = 0.737; t = 0.336)

The results are shown in the Table below

Sl. no	Hypotheses	“p” -value	“t”-value	Results
1	H1	0.465	0.731	Rejected
2	H2	0.140	1.480	Rejected
3	H3	0.034	2.129	Accepted
4	H4	0.737	0.336	Rejected

Based on the study, inferences are drawn as follow:

1. There exists a robust correlation between CSFs and Sustainability.
2. To safeguard sustainability organizations should focus on CSFs.

Managerial implications from the case studies

The case studies were an enlightening experience for the management. The knowledge and its interpretation gave the participants confidence to make decisions about the process. All those involved welcomed the new tools and techniques as they were able to make scientifically-based judgments, rather than intuitional ones. This modified the mentality and thinking process.

LSS studies have convinced the management about the need for specialized training for the organization 's employees. Thus, in all three departments where the case study was conducted, management formed a new team with senior doctors and few selected supporting staff as members to initiate improvement projects. In addition, for selected staff of different departments, the hospital management organized training sessions on LSS instruments and techniques, with the

current study as an example, to identify opportunities for LSS improvement in their respective departments. In addition, they introduced a reward scheme for the organization's successful LSS projects and decided to add LSS as an evaluation point for all employees.

The projects increased the skill level of the workers and they were able to easily use Lean principles and statistical tools in their regular enhancement initiatives. Ultimately, by engaging everybody in the institution for quality, the initiative brought a cultural change.

The study concludes that with respect to LSS, the healthcare industry in India is still in the early stages of evolution. In Indian hospitals, reform programs are not based on the tools and techniques of industrial engineering. This is partly due to the lack of engineering contact with medical practitioners. Cross-functional coordination between engineering and medical institutions will effectively tackle this. The successful use of tools and techniques for industrial engineering in the health sector could be encouraged by partnerships. Efficient implementation of simple hospital projects can allow practitioners to address harder measures in the future and to drive change on a wide scale. LSS can be seen as a forum for cultural and organizational change initiation, contributing to the complete transformation.

For drastic modifications to the procedure, LSS offers the principles, techniques, and methods in a more organized way. In addition, the DMAIC five-phase method is an efficient sequence that connects statistical and other measures that have been shown to be effective in process improvement. It is also evident that simulation-based LSS helps reduce implementation time and resources. It is evident from the study that LSS concepts adapted to the local culture of the people in the organization will contribute to behavioral changes and lasting improvements in the system. Such changes are not uniform, and are driven by the leadership and engagement of the people involved with the process. In addition, the LSS approach brings about a cultural shift in the organization by including everyone in the organization. The successful implementation and astonishing results of the case studies led to the conclusion that LSS is one of the best methods to improve the quality and reduce the waste, which is led by age old Lean thinking principles and the number driven statistical methods.

LIMITATIONS

The main limitation is the fact that, the study was conducted in a single dental college, based on a single location. But its noteworthy that the selected district is a hub for medical, dental and engineering colleges. The case studies were conducted in a real setting where patient arrival or discharge couldn't be controlled for the sake of experiment.

There was a specific timeframe to complete the research and none of the dental colleges were proficient in LSS implementation. Therefore, only three case studies conducted in a dental college were involved in the study. Therefore, the generalization of the particular findings of the analysis is limited.

However, because most other departments in dental college are more or less identical in terms of the atmosphere and work culture, the structure created may be used effectively for the entire sector. At the same time, for both the manufacturing and service industries, the methodology adopted and the learning from this research can be generalized.

FUTURE SCOPE

Future researchers can focus on increasing the sample size and focus on areas like customer satisfaction, customer retention, service quality etc. Further, researchers can undertake structured surveys in institutions based on affiliation, intake etc. and find the most important KPIs, CSFs, CTQ and STTs.

Future research may also include innovative methods that are tried and tested in manufacturing industry.

Furthermore, in order to gain greater insight into the progress and benefits of these measures in the Indian healthcare field, the researcher plans to incorporate the LSS system in the coming years. This will assist in the validation of the system and development.

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